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TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

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FIRST TRIALS COMPLETED

The first trials of TrialsNet’s use cases have been completed in this forth semester of activity. [The first trial](#) has been the one of UC5 “Control Room in the Metaverse” which has been successfully conducted in Turin on 15th October 2024. The trial demonstrated the use of a collaborative Metaverse Control Room that can be accessed by the security and safety forces from any location through VR headsets and/or tablets. There, the various officers can coordinate between them and receive real-time information from the location of the accident. The trial involved eighteen officers from five security agencies in Turin, including 112 (emergency switchboard), 118 (ambulances), police, fire brigade, and civil protection, simulating an emergency situation in the Park of Valentino. The trial leveraged the current deployment of public 5G network, a camera, a drone, two people-counting sensors and four portable devices. Officers expressed positive feedback regarding the proposed tool and functionalities, while also suggesting possible enhancements for the solution.

[The second trial](#) was the one of UC12 “City Parks in Metaverse” conducted on November 14th and 15th in Turin, involving around 140 people, including art high school students, teachers, and staff. The experience included five different phases (AR park walk, VR combat, quiz on the historical cultural aspects of the visit, VR visit of the Borgo Medioevale castle, and KVIs questionnaire filling) aiming at demonstrating the applications and innovative platforms developed by the project to implement the use case. The integration among the involved partners and users worked very well, resulting in a positive experience for all. Both KPIs and KVIs were measured and possible use case’s enhancements were also identified.

Still in Turin, in November, the Open Call sub-project “[Turin5Games](#)” performed its first trial in a shopping center, allowing users to play popular video games over multiple gaming stations equipped with mobile phones and TVs. The sub-project selected several video games such as Tiebreak, Fifa 24, WTA, and GTA5, running over a cloud-gaming platform deployed on two servers located in Milan (Italy) and Zurich (Switzerland), while exploiting the 5G network to provide the connectivity.

All these activities in the city of Turin, together with the other use cases which will shortly perform their trials there (i.e., UC13 “Extended XR Museum Experience” and the sub-projects “CITY4ALL”, “Torino4U”, “DREAMPARK”, “Remember Ascari: MR in MAUTO”, and “Cities Without Barriers” from the Open Call), which contribute to different application and innovation areas in the context of smart city and various domains such as security and safety, culture, tourism, and entertainment, have demonstrated how it is possible to achieve an efficient and fruitful collaboration between public administration, private enterprises, and research institutions, and contributed to the award of Turin as “[European Capital of Smart Tourism 2025](#)” and “[European Capital on Innovation 2024-25](#)” by the European Commission.

TRIALSNET ACTIVITIES ARE PROGRESSING

Besides the trials of UC5 and UC12, TrialsNet’s partners continued to work on all the other use cases, finalizing the development of the related applications including final tests and pre-trial activities, as well as on the deployment of the infrastructures in some sites.

In particular, in the use cases of Madrid cluster (i.e., namely UC1, UC6 and UC10), pre-trials have been performed throughout all the semester with all the partners involved over a 5G private infrastructure fully operating on mmWave (high-band 5G frequencies) and a SA (Stand-Alone) architecture based on Ericsson’s cutting-edge solutions without the need of anchor cells, as the user equipment (UE) is attached directly in the 5G SA network.

The tests peaked in November at the *Ericsson Imagine Live* week in Madrid, where the infrastructure was showcased to customers from all the Spanish mobile

operators, as well as from new market segments, academic and research partners, technology firms, government representatives and university students.

Throughput data rates up to 4.6 Gbit/s in downlink and up to 440 Mbit/s in uplink, were achieved during the event, combined with latency values sustained around 4ms, with performances that are quite overtaking the ones provided by the current commercial 5G network on mid-band frequencies, therefore enabling a wide range of new use cases.

During the month of November, the project also hardly worked in the context of the Open Call activities. Besides the continuous monitoring of the activities through the monthly reports, TrialsNet organized 24 ad-hoc review meetings in which, based on the mid-term report provided at month 6, the sub-projects were requested to present their use cases, the implementation status, eventual demo, trials plans, and an overview of the addressed KPIs/KVIs, having then the opportunity to receive guidance and suggestions from the TrialsNet's experts in order to improve their work towards the successful fulfilment of their objectives.

PLENARY IN IASI

During the month of October 2024, TrialsNet Partners gathered in Iasi, Romania, for the project's 6th plenary meeting. Hosted by the Gheorghe Asachi Technical University in the wonderful venues of the City Hall and the University's Rectorate, the partners analyzed the outcome of the interim review and planned the following steps. They also shared the outcome of the first project trial (UC5 in Turin) and the resulting lessons learned. Partners also planned the incoming interim review of the Open Call sub-projects.

The meeting resulted in a unique moment of alignment among UCs and WPs, as well as an opportunity to discuss and collaborate. The following plenary meeting will be in March in Pisa.

TRIALSNET COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

During the past semester, TrialsNet organized and participated in various international events. During these events, different demos of TrialsNet's use cases were performed, having more than 250 attendants. Some of them were registered in videos, which are available on the project [YouTube channel](#).

Among the attended events, on September 27th, TrialsNet participated to the [European Night of Researchers - Bright Night 2024](#), in Pisa, where the project was presented, with a special focus on the innovative solutions based on smart tools for telepresence in the surgical field (i.e., UC7 "Remote Proctoring" and UC8 "Smart Ambulance"), to support and enhance the e-Health workflow.

Then, in October, TrialsNet was present at the [IEEE FNWF](#), in Dubai, where the different WP3 use cases were presented, together with their reference infrastructures, status and current results. A great opportunity to introduce the project to the present community (industry and academia), sharing challenges, solutions and opportunities. A paper was also presented, which can be found [here](#).

Finally, in November, TrialsNet has been invited to the co-creation event "From 5G to 6G: leveraging key trends and 5G evolution to shape 6G for vertical sectors", at the [5G Techritory](#) conference held in October 2024, in Riga, Latvia, where presented an overview of the project, as one of the four Stream D projects of the Call 1, and took part the final Panel session as a good opportunity to exchange views and the challenges related to the trial implementation activities.

During the 5G Techritory conference, TrialsNet also participated to the recording of a podcast organized by SNS ICE entitled "[Lessons learned hosting vertical experiments from the perspective of 5G/6G experimental facilities](#)". The goal for this podcast was to gather 'hands-on' experts from each of the Phase 1 Stream D projects, to discuss their experience and insights and to participate in a panel with other experts, answering key questions on specific items such as the issues and obstacles in deploying vertical applications in 5G testbeds, the technological gaps between testbed providers and vertical

developers that hinder deployment, the common services/tools to be provided to vertical experimenters for deployment and testing, and others.

Details about TrialsNet participation in other events during this period could be found in the [Events section](#) of the project webpage.

PROJECT'S INFORMATION

If you are looking for further info about the project structure, consortium, the different use cases, as well as news and contacts, the [project website](#) is the place to go. The project deliverables, publications, together with other dissemination and communication material, are available on the corresponding [website section](#).

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